

plot design with N in the main plots and sources in the subplots.

Seedlings of Lalat (Obs 677/IR2071//Vikram/W1263, 130d duration group) were transplanted on 22 Jan. All plots received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha with all the LGU, NCU, RPU, SCU, and 1/3 the PU at transplanting. All the USG was placed 7 cm deep at 10 d after transplanting (DT). The additional PU was applied in equal splits at 20 DT and at panicle initiation.

Yields increased significantly with increasing N up to 112.5 kg N/ha (Table 1), although yield response (kg grain/kg N) and apparent N recovery values (Table 2) were highest at 37.5 kg N. Yields with USG and SCU were equal and significantly superior to those with other N sources. USG at 75 kg N/ha was the best treatment, as is reflected in yield response and apparent N recovery. □

Table 1. Grain yield with urea-based N sources. Bhubaneswar, India, 1986 dry season.

Nitrogen dose (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)						
	PU	USG	LGU	NCU	RPU	SCU	Mean
0	2.2	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.1	2.4	2.2
37.5	3.4	4.3	3.5	3.9	3.9	3.7	3.8
75.0	4.5	5.5	4.4	4.3	3.9	5.0	4.6
112.5	5.5	5.5	4.7	5.1	5.3	6.2	5.4
150.0	5.6	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.3	5.5	5.5
Mean	4.2	4.6	4.0	4.2	4.1	4.5	4.3
LSD (0.05) N:0.6, Source: 0.3. Sources at fixed N: 0.7 and N at the same or different source: 0.9							

Table 2. Yield response and apparent N recovery with urea-based N sources. Bhubaneswar, India, 1986 dry season.

Nitrogen dose (kg/ha)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Source		
			Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Apparent N recovery (%)	
37.5	41.6	51.4	PU	28.0	44.7
75.0	31.7	39.3	USG	38.1	54.2
112.5	28.0	42.7	LGU	26.6	32.6
150.0	21.7	40.2	NCU	30.1	41.9
			RPU	28.6	39.5
			SCU	33.1	47.5

Effect of urea supergranule (USG) on grain yield of varieties of different durations

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We studied the influence of USG on varieties of different durations in controlled irrigated experiments 1984-

Table 1. Mean grain yield of irrigated six long-duration varieties with USG and split applications of prilled urea. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1984	1985
Best split (prilled urea)	5.8	4.9
Four splits (prilled urea)	5.3	4.6
USG at 7 DT	5.5	5.1
1/4 N as prilled urea (basal) + 3/4 N as USG at 28 DT	-	5.1
3/4 N as USG at 7 DT + 1/4 N as prilled urea at panicle initiation	-	5.3
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.2
CV (%)	7.1	6.8

85. Recommended P, K, and Zn were applied before field puddling, N was applied as per treatment. The soil was a Vertisol type with pH 8.2, CEC 49.2 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.09% total N, and 5 ppm available P.

Short-duration (95-105 d) IET7564, IET7613, IET7614, and IET7566 were evaluated with 90 kg N/ha using USG placement and prilled urea split application. Source of N was not significant (3.94.4 t/ha).

Table 2. Effect of modified urea materials on grain yield of Rasi. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984 kharif.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Urea best split	4.6
USG at 7 DT	5.8
Mussoorie-phos-coated urea	4.8
Gypsum-coated urea	4.8
Neem cake-coated urea	4.4
Urea 4 equal splits (1/4 N basal + 1/4 N before panicle initiation + 1/4 N after panicle initiation + 1/4 N panicle stage)	4.5
Compost + USG (1/2 N as USG)	4.8
CD (0.05)	0.8
CV (%)	9.4

In longduration (150-165 d) IET5897, IET5890, IET5656, Jagannath, Phalgun, and Pankaj, 90 kg N/ha as urea best split was superior or equal to USG placement at 7 d after transplanting (DT). Yields with 3/4 N as USG at 7 DT + 1/4 N as prilled urea at panicle initiation were significantly greater than yields with prilled urea best split (Table 1).

Medium-duration Rasi responded better to USG (90 kg N/ha) than to prilled urea and other coated materials (Table 2). □

Mussoorie rock phosphate (MRP) effects on yield

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MRP is an indigenous fertilizer material suitable for acid soils; it slowly and continuously releases available P.

We studied its availability to rice variety Phalgun in a field experiment

Effect of MRP on yield. Mangalore, India, 1983-85.

Treatment	Yield (kg/plot)		
	1983	1984	1985
<i>Main plot</i>			
Application on day of transplanting	3.72	0.97	1.96
7 DBT	3.89	1.11	2.07
14 DBT	3.71	1.22	1.97
21 DBT	3.71	1.08	1.95
F test	ns	ns	ns
SEm ±	0.10	0.08	0.03
CV (%)	10.62	27.73	5.74
<i>Subplot</i>			
0 kg P/ha	3.10	1.13	1.89
13.2 kg P/ha	3.77	1.11	1.97
26.4 kg P/ha	4.46	1.09	2.07
39.6 kg P/ha	3.83	1.04	2.03
F test ^a	**	ns	**
SEm ±	0.10	0.05	0.02
CV (%)	10.59	17.58	4.50
Interaction (main × sub)	ns	ns	ns

^a*** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.

conducted during kharif seasons 1983-85. Experimental site soils are yellowish brown (10 YR 7/6 dry), clay loam, strong medium subangular blocky, dry hard, moist firm, wet sticky, moderately slow permeability with pH 5.7. They are high in organic C (1.26%) and available P (82 kg/ha), but low in available K (50 kg/ha).

Four main treatments (application at 0, 7, 14, and 21 d before transplanting [DBT]) and 4 subtreatments (0, 13.2, 26.4, and 39.6 kg P/ha) were tested in a split-plot design. All plots received 100 kg N and 73 kg K/ha.

Net plot (5.76 m²) yields over a period of 3 yr are presented in the table. Although the yield increase with MRP applied 7 DBT was not significant, the yield difference with 26.4 kg P/ha was significant. The interaction between P level and time of application was not significant. □

Weed seedlings transplanted with rice seedlings reduce grain yield

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We observed that grass weed seedlings had been transplanted with rice

seedlings in two farmers' fields in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. We harvested 50 1-m² quadrats from areas in both fields where transplanted seedlings were contaminated with weed seedlings and 50 1-m² quadrats from areas where no weed seedlings had been transplanted.

In 1 field, yield from quadrats where an average of 29% of the hills were infested with *Echinochloa glabrescens*

was 372 g/m²; in areas where no weed seedlings were transplanted, the yield was 476 g/m². In the other field, yield from quadrats where an average 23% of the hills were infested with *Echinochloa oryzoides* was 434 g/m², 18% lower than the 530 g/m² yield where no infestation was observed.

Differences in yield between the weed-infested and weed-free hills were highly significant in both fields. □

Nitrogen sources and placement for irrigated rice

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We studied N source and placement method for irrigated rice on a clay loam soil with pH 8.3 and 0.6% organic matter.

Deep placement of urea supergranules (USG) gave a higher yield and was the

most efficient, but was not significantly different from incorporating urea in dry soil (see table). Efficiency of dry soil incorporation was on a par with deep placement of USG

Incorporating urea in puddled soil gave a significantly lower yield. Calcium ammonium nitrate incorporated in puddled soil had the lowest yield after control and was the least efficient. Yields were significantly higher with higher levels of fertilizer but fertilizer efficiency was higher at lower levels. □

Rice grain yield (variety IR6) and fertilizer efficiency as affected by different N sources and their methods of placement. Islamabad, Pakistan, 1982.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Fertilizer efficiency (kg yield/kg N used)
Control	3.2 f	—
46 kg N/ha as urea incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.0 d	41.2
46 kg N/ha as calcium ammonium nitrate incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	4.6 e	30.9
46 kg N/ha as urea all incorporated in dry soil ^c	5.6 c	53.5
46 kg N/ha as USG deep placed, 4 DT	5.6 c	54.2
92 kg N/ha as urea incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.6 c	26.4
92 kg N/ha as calcium ammonium nitrate applied in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.1 d	21.7
92 kg N/ha as urea all incorporated in dry soil ^c	6.4 ab	35.7
92 kg N/ha as USG deep placed, 4 DT	6.6 a	37.6
SE	1.1	—

^aPI = panicle initiation, DT = days after transplanting. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance by DMRT. ^cThe field was irrigated and planted after dry soil incorporation.

Phosphorus application in acid-sulfate soil

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In the Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta of Vietnam, acid-sulfate soils are found in 1.15 million ha, mostly in Kien Giang, Long An, Dong Thap, Hau Giang, and An Giang Provinces. Seedling mortality and poor crop growth due to extremely